

RURAL EDUCATION: PROSPECTS AND RETROSPECT

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Abstract:

When a child opens his eyes in this world, each and every parent's starts dreaming for the future of their child and they believe, education is a best way of doing it. One very important point need to be highlighted is that most of the students are not able to get through at 10th and 12th board exam classes because of their poor education at primary level, and this is troublesome issue for most of the parents, which also leads to their reluctance in sending their children to school. So it is clear these discussion that poor education system has a direct impact on rural youth as poor education at primary level does not allow the access to higher education and the fraction of youth who get access to higher education remain less competitive. Education in the rural sector still remains largely dependent on the government, though private players are entering the field in large numbers.

Introduction:

When a child open his eyes in this world, each and every parent starts dreaming for the better future of their child and they believe, education is best way of doing it. But in rural India, there is a different story on part of both parents and education system. Parents are the first school and there teaching plays an important part in individual's life. But it seems that first school in rural India is not aware enough to help their children in their studies as they are not well educated. Therefore in rural India, a large number of parents are reluctant towards educating their children. On the part of the parents, the problem is that they believe that offering free education up to 8th standard is not enough for their children to be employed and the level of education i.e. higher education or professional education which might help in getting employment cannot be afforded by them. So they are reluctant to send their children to attain education. Moreover, one very important point need to be highlighted is that most of the students are not able to get though at 10th and 12th board exam classes because of their poor education at primary level, and this is troublesome issue for most of the parents, which also leads to their reluctance in sending their children to schools. They think that it is a waste

of 8-9 years as they are not to get through at 10th or 12th. So it is very important to notice, poor education is more responsible than parents.

Now that question is, in spite of government efforts as nearly 83% villages and 94% of the population has a primary school within a distance of one kilometre (vimalaran chandran 2002), what are those factors which are stopping children in rural India to get qualitative education. The attitudes of children and teacher also affect the quality of schools. While the children living in rural areas continue to be deprived of a quality education, part of the reason is the lack of competent and committed teachers. A large number of teachers refuse to teach in rural areas and those that do are usually under quality. Many of teachers also lack the enthusiasm to teach because of their meagre salary.

As the lack of teachers creates many obstacles for children in rural school, another setback is the lack of resources which becomes detrimental to the learning process. These may be due to the lack of text books and access to technology. But because of the government norm of no Student should be failed till VIII class; these schools have 100% passing rate. But because of low quality primary level education, students do not get through secondary or senior secondary level which sends back a very negative message toward education children to rural society. But having such a poor education system, there are few students who get through 10th and 12th exam and reaches to further higher education level to become employable. Because one who passes senior secondary level doesn't make them get good salary packages. This problem is due to lack of vocational education also.

Even in the school, getting a pass in the exams is the priority, not learning. Even these schools fail in teaching various arts and in particular commonsense to children. Both the private and government school in smaller town and village are uniformly pathetic. Even if a student graduates from a higher secondary school, there are not enough colleges. The only hope left to most high school graduates is correspondence education. It is not clear to me whether one can be motivated enough to student through the correspondence course material sitting at home. Even if one graduates from college, the graduates are mostly unemployable, because of poor quality course material and teaching in the colleges. So it is clear from the above discussion that poor education system has a direct impact on rural youth as poor education at primary level does not allow the access to higher education and the fraction of youth who get access to higher education remain less competitive.

Time to wake up:

“We are bumbling along with this out modelled system of education, which is a real shame.” These are the words of Krishna Kumar, former director of central institute of education in New Delhi. Ours is a country where the population has already reached more than one billion people, while only one-third of them are able to read. Due to various social, economic and educational factors India’s education program continues to be undercut. Now the question is how to improve and rejuvenate the education system, few things can be suggested as follows:-

- Firstly there is a need of efficient selection panel which make sure that competitive teachers have been selection to offer primary education, the reason to raise this point is because in the absence of corruption free selection panel, one cannot expect honest selection and it lead to incompetent selection of teacher.
- Secondly, government must set up performance based monitoring system. Poor performing schools should be penalised and performance parameters can be the performance of students in boards exams although there can be some more parameters in addition to this which needs a more in depth analysis.
- Thirdly, lots of good students end up with nothing in the absence good guidance system; therefore government should set up guidance centre in rural areas. These centres should be block wise or district wise and make sure they are easily accessible by rural youth.
- Libraries and reading rooms in rural areas should be strengthened.
- Vocational courses should be introduced in rural schools.
- Institutions like IITs and IIMs should be set up in the backward and rural areas to promote higher education.
- Before providing knowledge through computer related technologies, government should have to create knowledge on ICT education and its usage to the rural school students. Due to their lack of awareness in the field of ICTs, rural students do not pay interest in the computer based education. The awareness and motivation are needed not only for the students but also for the instructors of the ICT programme in rural schools.
- The higher education department should establish a placement cell in the directorate of collegiate education to cater to the needs of students of government colleges in rural areas. The directorate’s placement should give rural colleges’ access to

potential employers. Besides coordinating recruitment activities, the placement cell could encourage companies to make presentations for final-year students on the job market and the skills needed to succeed. The cell could also interact with the directorate of employment and training to spot job opportunities.

- Lastly; government should concentrate on above suggestions to improve the health of public education system because large rural population do not have access to private education because of their economic conditions. For this government should promote and make them aware of the scholarships specially meant for rural students.

Rural education must also include the following parameters:

- Self employment
- Productive education
- Inclination towards technical education
- Casting votes in favour of development of villages not in favour of castes and religion, means selecting a candidate who is keep for development
- Inclination towards proper primary and secondary education.
- To provide free standard education to rural children.
- Supporting children for higher education.
- Guiding and Supporting Research scholars in Educational Development.
- Implementing new teaching methodologies and Assessment system.
- Promoting all schools to stress free environment.
- Free education programs to poor people living in villages.
- To provide Free Internet facility.
- In our schools in rural side monthly once arrange seminar on any one topic example how to develop our communication
- In rural side must to teach spoken English. Because in this world English is very important. Most of the country speaking in English so rural side the government takes the step to provide free spoken English.
- Maintain rank card system. Giving gift to top ranking students.
- Extra caring to teach the poor students.
- Yearly twice arranges the industrial visit.
- Arrange the bus facility.

- Maintain uniform education for all states. The Government of Tamil Nadu has been implemented the Common School System is called “Samacheer Kalvi” or Tamil Nadu Uniform System of School Education or Equitable [education system](#). This is very good System. This System purpose is to make same quality syllabus which can stop discrimination based on economy, caste, religion and background for all school boards in Tamil Nadu. If we will have uniform education system in the states poor children can get more advantages of better education.
- Explore alternatives such as distance education programmes, virtual classrooms and internet education which will enable a paradigm shift in the delivery system of education.
- Encourage the Private-Public Partnership (PPP) model where private companies bring in efficient resource planning and execution capabilities while the Government provides necessary funds
- Tax benefits should be given to organizations which work in fields like R&D in Curriculum Design which will enable them to provide quality education at a reduced cost

Initiatives by Private Bodies working for Rural Education

Education in the rural sector still remains largely dependent on the government, though private players are entering the field in large numbers. Few of the initiatives by private bodies are really appreciable which are discussed below:-

- 1) **VidyaGyan** is an initiative of the Shiv Nadar Foundation -- set up by Shiv Nadar, founder of the technology group HCL. The first school has just opened, taking in 200 students from the fifth grade who scored the highest on the UP state board examinations. From the sixth grade onwards, they will study at VidyaGyan, a residential institute where all expenses are paid. The students are from economically challenged backgrounds, and VidyaGyan aims to mould them into leaders.
- 2) **Rishi Valley Education Centre** is located in a chronic drought area, in the rural interior of South India. The population consists of marginal farmers and shepherds. Rural Education Centre has been reaching out to a wider base of disadvantaged children: at first by establishing a network of "Satellite Schools" in villages scattered

throughout the surrounding countryside, and then by evolving a comprehensive education program based on its experience within those schools. More recently a vocational training facility has been set up where young adults can acquire locally employable skills in typing, carpentry and tailoring. This facility was sponsored by a capital grant from ICICI (Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India).

- 3) The Company, **GRAMIN AAROGYA VIKAS SANSTHA (GAVS)**, a Rural Health Development Organization, a registered public charitable trust established and promoted by the heritage company Glaxo India in April 1997 backed long-term unique project to set up a community college at Naya Gaon, Gurgaon to empower rural youths. This project was initiated in 2010 in partnership with Navjyoti India Foundation (NIF) founded by Dr. Kiran Bedi. The objective of this community college is to provide transformative, personal and skill based education to the marginalized and disadvantaged thereby enhancing employability and self reliance. Through this Community College the beneficiaries are registered to various need based as well as skill based academic programmes of IGNOU. GSK India supports the Community College project by providing education to 1000 rural youths to acquire specific knowledge or skills to make them self reliant.
- 4) Apart from providing basic education to all children, **P.R.I.D.E.** endeavours to continually improve the existing quality of education being imparted to the students. For the same, a School based Quality Improvement Program (SQIP) and Reading Improvement Program (RIP) were introduced for the creation of a physically and emotionally safe learning environment, through an improvement in community participation and ownership, improvement of infrastructure facilities, and improvement in overall learning levels of children in core curricular subjects. Study Centres for children in the 5th, 6th and 7th standards ensure that there is a conducive after-school environment for students to do their homework and practice what they have learnt at school.
- 5) **Super 30** is a highly ambitious and innovative educational program running under the banner of "Ramanujan School of Mathematics". It hunts for 30 meritorious talents from among the economically backward sections of the society and shapes them for India's most prestigious institution – the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT). In the last seven years, it has produced hundreds IITians from extremely poor background. During this program students are provided absolutely free coaching, lodging and food. Super 30 targets students from extremely poor families.

- 6) **Azim Premji Foundation** works to facilitate a **just, equitable, humane and sustainable** society which works in **education and related development areas** - both for direct impact and for their large positive multiplier.

Conclusion

According to recent statistics, nearly 241 million Indians will join the workforce by 2030. This gives India the potential to become a force to be reckoned with in the field of trained manpower. However, the source of this manpower-the education sector- still faces problems of access, equity and quality, especially in rural sector.

"Let us think of education as the means of developing our greatest abilities, because in each of us there is a private hope and dream which, fulfilled, can be translated into benefit for everyone and greater strength for our nation" - **John F. Kennedy**

The need for rural education can be easily understood by the above said statement by John F. Kennedy. Children in rural areas have great potential; they will flower if given the chance.

References:-

- "Education in the Rural Sector Still Remains Largely Dependent on Govt: Birla Shloka Edutech." *Education in the Rural Sector Still Remains Largely Dependent on Govt: Birla Shloka Edutech*. IndiaInfoline.com, 07 Mar. 2012. Web. 03 Aug. 2012. <<http://www.indiaonline.com/Markets/News/Education-in-the-rural-sector-still-remains-largely-dependent-on-govt-Birla-Shloka-Edutech/5370827308>>.
- "GlaxoSmithKline Pharmaceuticals Limited - Corporate Social Responsibility - Rural Projects." *GlaxoSmithKline Pharmaceuticals Limited - Corporate Social Responsibility - Rural Projects*. GSK Worldwide, n.d. Web. 01 Aug. 2012. <<http://www.gsk-india.com/corporate-ruralprojects.html>>.
- "GyanCentral." *GyanCentral*. N.p., n.d. Web. 01 Aug. 2012. <<http://www.gyancentral.com/articles/editorial/innovative-practices-for-rural-education-in-india>>.

"Our Vision | Azim Premji Foundation." *Our Vision / Azim Premji Foundation*. Azim Premji Foundation, n.d. Web. 01 Aug. 2012.

<http://www.azimpremjifoundation.org/Our_Vision>.

"Rishi Valley Rural Education Project." *Rishi Valley Rural Education Project*. N.p., n.d.

Web. 03 Aug. 2012. <<http://mithya.prasadkaipa.com/learning/rishi.html>>.

"Super30.org/index.html." *Super30.org/index.html*. Super 30 Ramanujan School of

Mathematics, n.d. Web. 03 Aug. 2012. <<http://www.super30.org/>>.

"VidyaGyan: A New Model for Improving Rural Education? - India Knowledge@Wharton."

VidyaGyan: A New Model for Improving Rural Education? - India

Knowledge@Wharton. IndiaKnowledge, 17 Dec. 2009. Web. 03 Aug. 2012.

<<http://knowledge.wharton.upenn.edu/india/article.cfm?articleid=4438>>.

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